

Criticality of Angle of Earthquake Shaking on Pounding Behaviour of Buildings

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Abstract Buildings with an insufficient separation gap (S_g) in either direction cause pounding effects between them and suffer damages, partially or entirely, depending on the shaking level. The level of damage increases with the direction of shaking and asymmetry. But code provisions usually place restrictions on separation gaps, considering the adjacent buildings. Hence, it is intended to check the provision's applicability for different directions of shaking, as most of the buildings in rural and urban areas are almost congested. Also, the effect is more prominent in stiff or flexible buildings. Two stiff buildings with 3 and 5 storeys are designed and detailed using IS 456, IS 1893-1, and IS 13920. Elastic and inelastic analyses are conducted (with and without including the effect of masonry walls as equivalent diagonal struts), and the direction of ground motion is varied from 0° , 30° , 45° , and 60° . Based on the maximum inelastic displacement, level of damages in structural elements, damage mechanism obtained from inelastic analyses, and S_g estimated using IS 1893-1, it is evidenced that the S_g specified in code provisions is insufficient. Also, the level of damage increases with the direction of the shaking. It is necessary to revise the separation gap specified in the building code provisions, including a minimum S_g based on limiting drift.

Keywords Pounding Effect, Separation Gap, Maximum Inelastic Displacement.

Introduction

In India, many strong earthquakes have been experienced in the recent past due to the tectonic movements under the subduction zone of the Indian plate, which resulted in huge losses of lives and properties. Also, due to the increasing population and growing cities in urban regions of India, buildings are constructed closely due to space restrictions. Under earthquake shaking, these buildings have the susceptibility to collide against each other (called pounding effects), causing damage to a particular storey or entire building depending upon the level of ground shaking. The buildings may hit against each other either laterally, orthogonally, or diagonally, depending on the symmetry of the building and the direction of shaking; this results in translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding between buildings. For example, damage due to translational pounding between buildings with varying heights during the 1999 Marmara (Turkey) earthquake and the 2015 Gorkha earthquake, and the orthogonal pounding during the 1983 Columbia earthquake caused huge damage in one building with only non-structural elements damage in the other building, Fig. 1 [Korkmaz, 2015; Shrestha and Hao, 2018; Mejia, 2017]. Usually, the worst effect of pounding is avoided by providing the required separation gap (S_g) between buildings. Thus, it is evident that S_g should be provided surrounding the buildings to avoid damage due to both translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding.

Fig. 1. Failure of buildings due to translational pounding during (a) the 1999 Marmara Earthquake, (b) the 2015 Gorkha Earthquake, and (c) orthogonal pounding during the 1983 Columbia Earthquake [Korkmaz, 2015; Shrestha and Hao, 2018; Mejia, 2017]

Buildings without sufficient S_g show different dynamic characteristics under earthquake shaking based on their natural periods and undergo pounding. This effect is more pronounced in buildings (i) with soft or weak storeys, which demand huge drifts; (ii) located in weak soil, causing liquefaction; and (iii) due to the torsional effects of an unsymmetrical plan or a non-uniform distribution of structural elements. The adjacent buildings with the same floor levels are damaged by hitting at floor levels, whereas in buildings with different floor levels, the floor of one building may hit the vertical elements like walls or columns, causing damage at a specific level. Also, in buildings with complex plan geometries, the separation joints provided between building blocks must have sufficient S_g specified by building code provisions [Korkmaz, 2015]. Overall, pounding effects arise in buildings due to (i) limited or no

separation gap, (ii) different building heights, (iii) different floor levels, (iv) impact from already collapsed buildings, (v) type of structural system, (vi) different total mass, (vii) insufficient gap near expansion joints of different blocks of the same buildings, and (viii) ground motion characteristics and their directions [Shrestha and Hao, 2018; Jing et. al., 2020; Langlade et. al., 2021]. Buildings with equal floor heights show less damage than buildings with different floor heights under earthquake effects. Also, the influence of pounding is greater in lighter buildings, and the effect of the incidence angle highly influences the response. Hence, the direction of earthquake shaking should be considered while studying the response due to pounding effects. The pounding effects shall be reduced by using dampers or completely isolating the building from the ground [Jing et. al., 2020; Kazemi et. al., 2021]. But studies fail to check the responses of buildings in diagonal directions and check the applicability of S_g provided in the building code provisions. Building code provisions endorse S_g between two adjacent buildings or from boundary lines (Table 1). It is expressed (i) using the sum (absolute or square root of the sum of squares, SRSS) of maximum inelastic displacements of two buildings estimated from the product of the elastic displacement of each building multiplied by the corresponding response reduction factor, R (e.g., ESEE, EBCS-8-95, E. 030, IS 1893-1); sometimes it may be enlarged with an amplification factor (2/3 to 2); or (ii) by limiting drift as a percentage of height (e.g., AS1170.4). A few code provisions additionally place restrictions on drift in the buildings, or a minimum S_g . Thus, it is required to check the applicability of these provisions for translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding by varying the angle of shaking and providing revised guidelines. The infill walls contribute to the lateral stiffness of buildings and reduce displacement between buildings under pounding actions. Therefore, it is necessary to account for the infill wall contribution while checking the provisions for pounding. A set of buildings having 3- and 5-stories is considered with and without including the infill walls as an equivalent strut. The elastic and inelastic behaviour is studied using modal, equivalent static, nonlinear static, and nonlinear dynamic analyses. Subsequently, the S_g required based on the maximum considered earthquake is calculated based on inelastic analyses and compared with the code calculated S_g for translational pounding. Yet again, it is checked for orthogonal and diagonal pounding by varying the incidence angle of earthquake shaking. Lastly, design recommendations are provided for pounding.

Table 1. Comparison of S_g provided in building code provisions

Code Provisions	Provisions on Pounding	Upper limit on S_g
EBCS-8-95, 1983 (Ethiopia)	(a) Buildings from boundary: $S_g = 2\delta_{max}$ (b) Adjacent buildings: $S_g = 2(\delta_{max,1} + \delta_{max,2})$ where, $\delta_{max} = 3\delta_e$	Adjacent buildings, $\delta_e < 0.005H$
ESEE, 1988 (Egypt)	(a) Buildings from boundary: $S_g = 2\delta_{max}$ (b) Adjacent buildings: $S_g = 2(\delta_{max,1} + \delta_{max,2})$ where, $\delta_{max} = 3\delta_e$	(a) Buildings from boundary: $S_g \geq 0.02H$ and not $< 2.5cm$ (b) Adjacent buildings: $S_g \geq 0.04H$ and not $< 5cm$
IS 1893-1, 2016 (India)	(a) Adjacent buildings: $S_g = \delta_{max,1} + \delta_{max,2}$ where, $\delta_{max} = R\delta_e$	Not specified
AS1170.4, 2007 (Australia)	Buildings $> 15m$: Provide structural walls or S_g from boundary $> 1\%H$	Not specified
E.030, 2016 (Peru)	$S_g = \frac{2}{3}(\delta_{max,1} + \delta_{max,2})$ where, $\delta_{max} = \gamma\delta_e$; $\gamma = 0.75R$ and R for regular and irregular buildings	$S_g \geq (0.006h \geq 0.03m)$

Note: δ_e is the maximum elastic displacement; δ_{max} , the maximum inelastic displacement; R , the response reduction factor; H , the height of building.

Numerical Study

The elastic behaviour of buildings is studied using Modal Analysis MA and Equivalent Static Analysis ESA, whereas the inelastic behaviour is studied using Nonlinear Static Analysis NLPoA and Nonlinear Time History Analysis NLTHA. ETABS is used for elastic analysis, and Perform 3D is used for inelastic analysis [ETABS Ultimate 2022; Perform 3D, 2021]. The responses for translational, orthogonal, and diagonal poundings are

obtained by varying the angle of shaking of ground motions (0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°). The S_g is estimated using code-based expressions and inelastic analyses, to suggest recommendations for the building codes.

Building Configurations and Arrangements

A set of buildings with 3- and 5-storey buildings is considered to check the applicability of code provisions (Fig. 2). Buildings having 3- and 5-storey models without struts are named 3SWoS and 5SWoS; similarly, buildings having 3- and 5-storey models with diagonal struts are named 3SWS and 5SWS, respectively. All buildings have a 3 m storey height and a 4 m bay length. The size of beams and columns is uniform along height. The sizes of beams are 300 mm × 400 mm for all buildings, whereas the sizes of columns are 400 mm × 400 mm in 3-storey buildings and 500 mm × 500 mm in 5-storey buildings. To account for the cracked section properties, the stiffness modifiers used for beams and columns are 0.35- and 0.70-times gross cross-sections. Slabs and wall thicknesses are taken as 150 mm and 250 mm, respectively. The unit weight of infill walls is 20 kN/m³. At the roof top, a parapet wall of 1 m is considered. Also, additional loads considered for floor finish, live load, and roof live load are 1 kN/m², 3 kN/m², and 1.5 kN/m², respectively. Concrete of grade M30 and Fe 415 steel is used. Buildings are in seismic zone V (0.36 g) and have hard rock-type soil. The importance factor and Response are taken as 1 and 5, respectively [IS 1893-1, 2016]. With uniform mass distribution, the floor diaphragms are assumed to be rigid. Buildings are designed for lateral loads based on ESA using code calculated natural periods following the provisions of IS 456 and IS 13920. The same buildings are used to study the response with and without including the diagonal struts, as the loads from infill walls are considered while designing the buildings. All buildings have ≥80% mass participation in X- and Y-directions. Also, the elastic drift is within 0.4% [IS 1893-1, 2016].

Fig. 2. 3- and 5-storey buildings with and without diagonal struts

In urban areas, buildings are constructed without sufficient gaps all around them. Therefore, under earthquake shaking, it may induce translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding between buildings, resulting in huge damage. To demonstrate various possibilities of pounding, the buildings are arranged as shown in Fig. 3. Under purely X-directional shaking, Buildings I and II or III and IV will undergo translational pounding; when the direction of shaking is in the Y-direction, Buildings I and IV or II and III will undergo orthogonal pounding. Subsequently, if the angle of shaking of ground motion (GM_θ) varies (like 30° and 60°), along with translational and orthogonal pounding (between I, II, and IV), diagonal pounding (between I and III) is induced due to torsional effects. It may cause damage to all four buildings (I, II, III, and IV). Sometimes, if GM_θ is 45°, Buildings I and III hit in a diagonal direction, causing purely diagonal pounding. These are used for checking the susceptibility of other types of pounding in buildings.

The inelastic behaviour of these buildings is studied, including the inelastic behaviour of materials like concrete and steel. Confined concrete property is used for core concrete to account for confinement due to transverse steel and unconfined concrete for cover [Mander et. al., 1988]. Beams are modelled by the lumped plasticity approach using idealized moment curvature for yielding of steel and ultimate failure by core crushing of concrete [Sunitha et. al., 2016]. Alternately, columns are modelled by the fiber modelling approach using the idealized stress-strain characteristics of concrete and steel. Ultimately, building failure is declared by failure in the extreme layer of confined concrete when it reaches the limiting strain in bending compression. Also, only flexural deformations are considered, and the effect of P-Δ is ignored. Under cyclic actions, all the elements are expected to track the elastoplastic backbone curve without any stiffness degradation or strength deterioration. Yielding of structural elements is professed when they attain their ≥80% yield strain or curvature and ultimately fail when they reach their ≥80% ultimate strain or curvature. The nonlinear static analysis is validated in Perform 3D using an experimentally tested one bay frame using the aforesaid properties

[Vecchio and Emar, 1992]. The variation in initial stiffness, ultimate deformation, and peak strength is about 6%, 3%, and 10%, respectively. The infill walls are modelled as an equivalent strut in elastic and inelastic analyses [IS 1893-1, 2016; Panagiotakos and Fardis, 1996]. Also, the inelastic property is assigned at the center of struts, with edges being pinned to the ends of beam-column joints.

Fig. 3. Possible arrangement of buildings in plan for translational (I and II), orthogonal (I and IV, II and III), and diagonal (I and III) poundings of various combinations of 3- and 5-storey buildings

Elastic and Inelastic Behaviour

The natural periods (T_x and T_y) estimated from IS 1893-1 are used in the estimation of base shear (V_x and V_y) and elastic displacements in X- and Y-directions using ESA (Table 2). The natural period considered in the estimation of base shear is the same in buildings with and without struts. Therefore, 3- and 5- storey buildings with and without struts show similar base shear. But the elastic displacement (δ_e) varies; buildings with struts show lesser displacements than buildings without struts. Thus, the absence of infill walls highly underestimates the building's lateral stiffness, but it is inherently considered in the estimation of natural periods. Additionally, inelastic analyses are required to exactly predict the behaviour of buildings and check their susceptibility to pounding.

Table 2. Properties of considered buildings from elastic analyses.

BC	T_x or T_y (s)	V_x or V_y (kN)	R	$\delta_e = \Delta_x$ or Δ_y (m)
3SWoS	0.2025	894.6	5	0.02438
5SWoS	0.3375	1604.3	5	0.07822
3SWS	0.2025	894.6	5	0.00299
5SWS	0.3375	1604.3	5	0.00015

The inelastic behaviour of these buildings is studied using Nonlinear Static Analysis NLPoA and Nonlinear Time History Analysis NLTHA (for $GM_\theta = 0^\circ$). In NLPoA, buildings are pushed laterally for 4% inelastic drift based on a code based lateral load profile. The capacity curve is obtained and expressed using normalized lateral strength (V/W , where V is lateral strength and W is seismic weight) and roof drift Δ (in percentage). The performance point (PP) is estimated using ATC-40 for the maximum considered earthquake (MCE) and marked in the capacity curve (Fig. 4). On the other hand, NLTHA is conducted using seven critical far-field ground motions (GM01: Coalinga – Parkfield (Fault Zone 3), GM02: Imperial Valley – Coachella Canal#4, GM03: Landers – Pal Springs Airport, GM04: Loma Prieta – Salinas (John and Work), GM05: Northridge – LA 116th Street School, GM06: San Fernando – LA (Hollywood Stor Lot), GM07: Superstition Hills (B) – Wildlife Lique. Array) [Huang et. al., 2011; Reyes et. al., 2014]. All the ground motions are scaled to building natural period based on the IS 1893-1 spectrum. The maximum inelastic drift Δ_m is estimated from the average of seven ground motion responses and shown in Fig. 4; in a few cases, Δ_m exactly matched the PP; hence, it is not marked separately. The levels of damages in structural elements at PP of NLPoA and NLTHA are given in Table 3; the damages are specified in ranges for NLTHA as they vary with ground motions. Also, the damage mechanism (yielding and ultimate failure of structural elements) at the PP of NLPoA and under NLTHA for GM03 is shown in Fig. 5. The following observations are obtained based on the normalized capacity curve, level of damage in structural elements, and damage mechanism at MCE demand (Figs. 4 and 5, Table 3):

- (i) Buildings with struts (3SWS and 5SWS) show more lateral stiffness and strength than buildings without struts (3SWoS and 5SWoS), but they show lesser deformability. 3-storey buildings (3SWS and 3SWoS) have more lateral strength than 5-storey buildings (5SWS and 5SWoS). Also, 3SWS has more deformability than 5SWS (Fig. 4).

(ii) PP of NLPoA and Δ_m from NLTHA almost lie on the verge of yielding for almost all buildings (Fig. 4). Thus, the level of damage in these buildings is marginal. Buildings with struts (3SWS and 5SWS) show lesser damage in beams and columns, with damage confined to diagonal struts (~40% yielded and ~30% struts completely failed under NLTHA, e.g., 5SWS). But buildings with struts (3SWoS and 5SWoS) show more damage to beams and columns. Sometimes, ~50% of beams have completely failed under NLTHA, losing their gravity load carrying capacity (e.g., 3SWoS) (Fig. 5 and Table 3).

(iii) The level of damages shall be acceptable for the MCE demand as the failed structural elements may be retrofitted. But under the action of pounding, the level of damage to structural elements will be greater due to the impact between two buildings. But this study does not account for the impact between two buildings; rather, it aims to estimate the applicability of the provided S_g based on code provisions and check the susceptibility of pounding.

Fig. 4. Capacity curve marked with PP and Δ_m from NLTHA of 3- and 5-storey buildings

Table 3. Comparison of damages in structural elements with NLPoA and NLTHA at MCE demand ($GM_0 = 0^\circ$).

Analyses	BC	Beams (%)		Columns (%)		Struts (%)	
		Yielding	Ultimate	Yielding	Yielding	Ultimate	
NLPoA	3SWoS	50	11.7	33.3	-	-	
	5SWoS	50	0	16	-	-	
	3SWS	33.3	0	26.7	22.1	16.7	
	5SWS	0	0	4	20	15	
NLTHA	3SWoS	41 – 50	0 – 50	0 – 67	-	-	
	5SWoS	48 – 50	0 – 47	0 – 76	-	-	
	3SWS	0 – 17	0	0	0 – 17	0 – 17	
	5SWS	0 – 20	0	0 – 20	29 – 39	0 – 30	

Effect of Incidence Angle of Shaking

The susceptibility of pounding (translational, orthogonal, and diagonal) changes with the direction of ground motions, as it is highly unpredictable. Therefore, NLTHA is conducted on all buildings independently with varying GM_0 (0° , 35° , 45° , and 60°) with respect to the X-axis (Fig. 3). The level of damage to structural elements under MCE demands is shown in Table 4. The damage mechanism with varying GM_0 of 5SWS is shown in Fig. 6. The following observations are made from this study (Table 4 and Fig. 6):

Fig. 5. (a) and (b) yielding and ultimate damages of structural elements under NLPoA at PP; (c) and (d) yielding and ultimate damages of structural elements under NLTHA for GM03 along X-direction ($GM_0 = 0^\circ$) of 5-storey buildings without and with struts (3SWoS and 5SWS)

Table 4. Comparison of damages in structural elements with varying GM_0 under NLTHA at MCE demand.

BC	GM_0	Beams (%)		Columns (%)	Struts (%)	
		Yielding	Ultimate	Yielding	Yielding	Ultimate
3SWoS	0°	41 – 50	0 – 50	0 – 67	-	-
	30°	50 – 100	0 – 50	0 – 33	-	-
	45°	67 – 100	0 – 67	0 – 33	-	-
	60°	50 – 100	0 – 50	0 – 33	-	-
5SWoS	0°	48 – 50	0 – 47	0 – 76	-	-
	30°	53 – 100	0 – 22	0 – 35	-	-
	45°	80 – 100	0	0 – 45	-	-
	60°	53 – 100	0 – 22	0 – 35	-	-
3SWS	0°	0 – 17	0	0	0 – 17	0 – 17
	30°	0	0	0	0 – 35	0 – 16
	45°	0	0	0	0 – 35	0
	60°	0	0	0	0 – 35	0 – 16
5SWS	0°	0 – 20	0	0 – 20	29 – 39	0 – 30
	30°	0 – 8	0	0 – 46	30 – 64	0 – 32
	45°	0	0	0 – 2	44 – 68	0 – 49
	60°	0 – 6	0	0 – 28	30 – 64	0 – 32

(i) The level of damage to structural elements increases from 0° to 45° and decreases thereafter for buildings without struts (e.g., 3SWoS and 5SWoS). As the building is symmetrical in both X- and Y-directions, the level of damage remains the same at $GM_0 = 30^\circ$ and 60° . Almost 100% of beams yielded, and $\geq 50\%$ of them completely failed; 33 to 76% of columns yielded without any complete failure in them. Retrofitting complete buildings becomes highly uneconomical rather than going for new construction (Table 4).

(ii) Buildings with struts (3SWS and 5SWS) show less damage than buildings without struts (3SWoS and 5SWoS). Acceptable level of damages is noticed in 3SWS with ~35% yielding and 17% ultimate failure of struts; in contrast, ~70% yielding and 50% ultimate failure of struts in 5SWS shows that almost this building will behave as like without struts, e.g., 5SWoS. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the influence of both bare frame and infill walled framed buildings while studying the effect for pounding (Table 4 and Fig. 6).

(iii) Again, this study does not account for the impact between two buildings, where the level of damage could be greater. Hence, it is necessary to study the applicability provided by S_g for various pounding effects with varying GM_0 .

Fig. 6. (a) and (b) yielding and ultimate damages of structural elements GM03 by varying $GM_\theta = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ,$ and 60° of 5-storey buildings with struts (5SWS)

Comparison with Building Code Provisions

To check the susceptibility of pounding, two buildings (named B_1 and B_2) are assumed to be arranged adjacent to each other. Six different combinations are obtained by choosing combinations of 3- and 5-storey buildings (Table 5). Using their corresponding elastic displacements (δ_{e1} & δ_{e2}) and response reduction factors (R_1 and R_2), S_g provided ($S_{g,p}$) in IS 1893-1 is calculated (using expressions given in Table 1). Conversely, S_g required ($S_{g,r}$) from NLPoA and NLTHA (for $GM_\theta = 0^\circ$) for MCE demand is calculated using the sum of maximum inelastic displacements of each building (using inelastic displacement at PP for NLPoA and mean value from 7 ground motions for NLTHA) (Table 5). $S_{g,p}$ is sufficient for buildings without struts (combinations of 3SWoS and 5SWoS buildings) and not for buildings without struts, as $S_{g,r}$ is greater than $S_{g,p}$ (values are bold and underlined). Similarly, considering the arrangements of 4 buildings (Fig. 3), S_g for translational (I and II), orthogonal (I and IV, II and III), and diagonal (I and III) poundings of various combinations of 3- and 5-storey buildings are compared. Again, six combinations of B_1 and B_2 will be obtained for all these cases (Table 6). The S_g required for translational (X-direction, named as $S_{g,rx}$), orthogonal (Y-direction, named as $S_{g,ry}$), and diagonal (named as $S_{g,rd}$) pounding is calculated using maximum inelastic displacement in X-, Y-, and diagonal directions (based on the mean value from 7 ground motions for NLTHA) by varying the GM_θ from $35^\circ, 45^\circ,$ and 60° with respect to the X-axis. Similarly, the S_g provided for purely translational (X-direction, named $S_{g,ptx}$), purely orthogonal (Y-direction, named $S_{g,pty}$), and purely diagonal (named $S_{g,pd}$) pounding is calculated using IS 1893-1. The SRSS of maximum translational displacements in X and Y directions is used for the diagonal direction. Yet again, the provided spacing is sufficient for buildings without struts (for combinations of 3SWoS and 5SWoS buildings, values are bold and underlined). Thus, additional restrictions are required for buildings with struts.

Table 5. Comparison of S_g from IS 1893-1 with NLPoA and NLTHA.

B_1	B_2	R_1	R_2	$\delta_{e1} (m)$	$\delta_{e2} (m)$	IS 1893 $S_{g,p} (m)$	$S_{g,r}$ from NLPoA			$S_{g,r}$ from NLTHA		
							$\Delta_{m1} (m)$	$\Delta_{m2} (m)$	$S_{g,r} (m)$	$\Delta_{m1} (m)$	$\Delta_{m2} (m)$	$S_{g,r} (m)$
3SWoS	3SWoS	5	5	0.0244	0.0244	<u>0.2440</u>	0.1078	0.1078	0.2156	0.0893	0.0893	0.1786
3SWoS	5SWoS	5	5	0.0244	0.0782	<u>0.5131</u>	0.1078	0.1250	0.2328	0.0893	0.1521	0.2412
5SWoS	5SWoS	5	5	0.0782	0.0782	<u>0.7822</u>	0.1250	0.1250	0.2499	0.1521	0.1521	0.3041
3SWS	3SWS	5	5	0.0001	0.0001	0.0015	0.0349	0.0349	<u>0.0698</u>	0.0087	0.0087	<u>0.0174</u>
3SWS	5SWS	5	5	0.0001	0.0030	0.0157	0.0349	0.0211	<u>0.0560</u>	0.0087	0.0284	<u>0.0371</u>
5SWS	5SWS	5	5	0.0030	0.0030	0.0299	0.0211	0.0211	<u>0.0421</u>	0.0284	0.0284	<u>0.0567</u>

Table 6. Assessment of S_g for translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding for different GM_θ .

GM _θ	B ₁	B ₂	S _{g,p} from IS 1891-1			S _{g,r} from NLTHA		
			S _{g,ptx} (m)	S _{g,pty} (m)	S _{g,pd} (m)	S _{g,rtx} (m)	S _{g,rtz} (m)	S _{g,rd} (m)
30°	3SWoS	3SWoS	0.2440	0.2440	0.3451	0.1504	0.0799	0.1674
	3SWoS	5SWoS	0.5131	0.5131	0.7256	0.2039	0.1083	0.2285
	5SWoS	5SWoS	0.7822	0.7822	1.1062	0.2574	0.1367	0.2896
	3SWS	3SWS	0.0015	0.0015	0.0021	0.0147	0.0081	0.0167
	3SWS	5SWS	0.0157	0.0157	0.0222	0.0312	0.0167	0.0353
	5SWS	5SWS	0.0299	0.0299	0.0422	0.0477	0.0254	0.0538
45°	3SWoS	3SWoS	0.2440	0.2440	0.3451	0.1224	0.1224	0.1567
	3SWoS	5SWoS	0.5131	0.5131	0.7256	0.1622	0.1623	0.2213
	5SWoS	5SWoS	0.7822	0.7822	1.1062	0.2021	0.2021	0.2858
	3SWS	3SWS	0.0015	0.0015	0.0021	0.0118	0.0118	0.0167
	3SWS	5SWS	0.0157	0.0157	0.0222	0.0247	0.0247	0.0349
	5SWS	5SWS	0.0299	0.0299	0.0422	0.0375	0.0375	0.0532
60°	3SWoS	3SWoS	0.2440	0.2440	0.3451	0.0798	0.1505	0.1673
	3SWoS	5SWoS	0.5131	0.5131	0.7256	0.1082	0.2038	0.2284
	5SWoS	5SWoS	0.7822	0.7822	1.1062	0.1366	0.2572	0.2894
	3SWS	3SWS	0.0015	0.0015	0.0021	0.0081	0.0147	0.0167
	3SWS	5SWS	0.0157	0.0157	0.0222	0.0167	0.0312	0.0353
	5SWS	5SWS	0.0299	0.0299	0.0422	0.0254	0.0477	0.0538

Recommendations for Design

The S_g provided in different code provisions (like ESEE, EBCS-8-95, and E.030) are compared with IS 1893-1. Additional restrictions for minimum S_g are provided based on a constant value or drift ratio (Table 1). Therefore, based on the maximum inelastic displacements of NLPoA and NLTHA (0°), the inelastic drift ratio is calculated by dividing it by height H; it varies from 0.006H to 0.007H. Therefore, a conservative estimate of 0.008H is selected. The proposed S_g is calculated considering the maximum values of (i) S_{g,p} (using IS 1893-1) and (ii) 0.008H. Finally, comparison with different code provisions evidence that (i) ESEE and proposed S_g are more conservative, (ii) EBCS-8-95 and IS 1893-1 are applicable for bare frame buildings, and (iii) E.030 is not satisfying buildings with and without struts (Table 7). Therefore, the normalized S_{gn} is obtained as (i) the ratio of proposed S_g with S_g from NLTHA, and (ii) the ratio of S_g from IS 1893-1 and S_g from NLTHA, for translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding of different combinations specified in Tables 5 and 6 for varying GM_θ (Fig. 7). The proposed modification for IS 1893-1, including 0.008H, shows S_{gn} > 1 having sufficient S_g between buildings in all directions.

Table 7. Comparison of S_g (in m) from different code provisions.

B ₁	B ₂	ESEE	EBCS-8-95	E.030	IS 1893-1	Proposed	NLPoA	NLTHA
3SWoS	3SWoS	0.3600	0.2928	0.1952	0.2440	0.2440	0.2156	0.1786
3SWoS	5SWoS	0.6157	0.6157	0.2149	0.5131	0.5131	0.2328	0.2414
5SWoS	5SWoS	0.9386	0.9386	0.6258	0.7822	0.7822	0.2499	0.3041
3SWS	3SWS	0.3600	0.0450	0.0540	0.0015	0.0720	0.0698	0.0174
3SWS	3SWS	0.3600	0.0450	0.0900	0.0157	0.1200	0.0560	0.0371
5SWS	5SWS	0.6000	0.0750	0.0900	0.0299	0.1200	0.0421	0.0567

Fig. 7. Comparison of S_g based on IS 1893-1 and proposed approach for translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding under varying $GM_0 = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, \text{ and } 60^\circ$ of combinations of 3- and 5-storey buildings.

Conclusions

Buildings in urban cities in India are constructed with limited spacing between them; hence, buildings may pound each other under earthquake shaking. Based on the direction of shaking, buildings may collide in translational, orthogonal, and diagonal directions. But building code provisions often describe the separation gap S_g between adjacent buildings and remain silent in other directions. Therefore, the applicability of code provisions is checked using the S_g provided for translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding. Therefore, the direction of ground motions is varied from $0^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, \text{ and } 60^\circ$. 3- and 5-storey buildings (with and without including the effect of infill walls as diagonal struts) are considered. Inelastic behaviour (based on capacity curve, level of damages in structural elements, and damage mechanism) of these buildings is studied using nonlinear static (NLPoA) and nonlinear dynamic time history (NLTHA) analyses under maximum considered earthquake. Based on the maximum inelastic displacement obtained from NLPoA and NLTHA, the S_g required between buildings is calculated. S_g provided using IS 1893-1 is not sufficient in buildings, including struts. Additional restrictions are required in addition to the existing provisions. Therefore, based on the observations from different code provisions (e.g., ESEE, EBCS-8-95, E.030), an additional restriction for minimum spacing based on drift ratio is proposed ($0.008H$, i.e., $0.8\%H$, where H is the height of the building). It is calculated based on the inelastic maximum displacement from NLPoA and NLTHA. S_g provided in India shall be revised as the maximum of (i) S_g based on IS 1893-1 and (ii) $0.008H$. It is confirmed by the various combinations of buildings with translational, orthogonal, and diagonal pounding. The study may be extended by modelling the building together, including the impact elements, as it may increase the damage to structural elements.

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